

The Center for Open Science’s Response to the Office of Management and Budget Proposed Rule: Regulation for Financial Assistance (Docket OMB-2026-0034)

Submitted on behalf of the Center for Open Science (COS) by Maryam Zaringhalam, Senior Director of Policy, and David Mellor, Senior Policy Analyst.

We are writing today on behalf of the [Center for Open Science](#) (COS), a non-profit organization dedicated to increasing the openness, integrity, and trustworthiness of research. Our advocacy efforts are rooted in our experience as: (a) an infrastructure provider through the Open Science Framework (OSF), which supports sharing of research plans, outputs, and outcomes across the research lifecycle; (b) an organization that performs research on research to understand contributors to reproducibility, efficiency, and integrity; and (c) policy experts in practices and processes that increase the openness, rigor, and reproducibility of scientific research. This work positions COS as an expert in policies promoting the transparency, accountability, and efficiency of scientific research, including tenets of the Executive Order on Restoring Gold Standard Science (GSS). Through this lens, we comment on the Office of Management and Budget’s (OMB) Proposed Rule: Regulation for Federal Financial Assistance, with particular attention to Federally funded research and development.

OMB’s justification for the proposed revisions to title 2 of the Code of Federal Regulations is to increase the transparency, accountability, and oversight of Federal awards. Several proposed changes, however, undermine this goal and are at odds with the Administration’s stated priorities around advancing GSS. Our comments are organized into two themes; an attached PDF provides detailed analysis and citations.

The regulation compromises the independence and integrity of Federally funded research by introducing senior political officials into the review and decision-making process. [200.202], [200.205], and [200.340] have the combined effect of embedding political influence across the grant lifecycle—from deciding what grant opportunities are available, how applicants are evaluated, and whether awards are canceled on broad discretionary grounds. [200.205] requires pre-issuance review by senior political officials, sidelining career subject-matter experts and demoting the weight of the merit review process. While [200.205] cites GSS, political pre-review is in direct conflict with the tenets that science must be “subject to unbiased peer review” and “without conflicts of interest.” Placing this control in political hands forces the research timeline onto the timeline of

politics, which can shift quickly, regardless of the evidence. This unpredictability is incompatible with rigorous research, creating the conditions under which researchers may fear that they—or their institutions—will be penalized if their findings prove politically inconvenient. [200.340] substantiates this fear: grants may be canceled if findings no longer fit “agency priorities or the national interest.”

The regulation limits the degree to which Federally funded researchers can freely and independently communicate their work, undermining OMB’s stated goals of increasing transparency and accountability. [200.432], [200.450], and [200.461] place limits on grant recipients' ability to present at conferences, communicate findings, and publish their work. These activities are core to research; they ensure findings reach the taxpayers funding them rather than stay locked in academic institutions. Provision [200.461] barring the use of Federal funds to pay article processing charges (APCs) is in direct conflict with agency public access policies referenced in GSS implementation plans, which permit such costs to enable free and immediate access to research results. Alternative models exist and should be encouraged; however, barring APCs outright disrupts academic communication, as does requiring agency pre-approval for conference attendance in [200.432]. [200.450(iv)] and [200.450(v)] restrict communication activity deemed “unrelated to” the funded work, but their vagueness may be construed to reach beyond advocacy into the ordinary dissemination of research findings to the public and decision-makers. The result is a chilling effect on research communication.

Across both themes, these provisions impose real costs on the independence, integrity, and free communication of results across the research enterprise. In its own Regulatory Impact Analysis, OMB concedes it “was unable to quantify the expected costs of the rule” and anticipates “minimal to modest to substantial short-term costs for recipients.” OMB also appears to underestimate these costs. Its analysis treats the pre-issuance review in [200.205] as having “no perceived impacts,” despite its requirement that senior appointees substantively review every discretionary award rather than deferring to the judgment of expert review panels. These are not costless—nor is it cost-saving to introduce greater political control over research. COS opposes OMB’s proposed updates discussed throughout our comments and strongly recommends OMB retain those provisions’ original language.